

A VARIATION IN THE DOWNING GOOSEBERRY

On a recent trip to northern Ohio my attention was called to certain gooseberry plants growing in a plantation of Downing. The general aspect of these plants and their fruit was not dissimilar to that of Downing but a closer examination revealed the difference in foliage shown in the illustration. The normal form has leaves nearly as broad as they are long, while the aberrant plants have long narrow leaves. This difference in foliage seems always to be associated with complete, or

nearly complete barrenness. The owner thought that the plants changed from one form to the other, but his son was of the opinion that both forms existed in the nursery stock. The one theory suggests the possibility of an obscure disease in the nursery similar to the "reversion" of black currants described in English publications. The other brings in the possibility of a spurious strain or variety, possibly like the off-type lemon trees found by Shamel in his citrus work. PAUL THAYER.